

Feasibility study for the utilization of natural gas and hydrogen blends on industrial furnaces

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Abstract. In the deep steel industry decarbonization, green hydrogen plays a pivotal role as alternative energy to replace natural gas and carbon bearing materials. In this frame, technical aspects and in general criticalities relevant to the use of mixtures of hydrogen and natural gas in industrial processes were investigated: in particular its effect was analyzed on employ of existing industrial burners for treatment furnace and on oxidability and descaling susceptibility of forged material as Grade F22V and Inconel[®] 625. The experimental campaign on burner using blends with 30% and 50%vol. of hydrogen in natural gas highlighted that it is possible to ignite the burner for both mixtures, but that the burner is more stable with the 30%vol. of hydrogen in natural gas. The detected emissions of nitrogen oxides compared to the natural gas increase up to 15%. The results indicated that selected high speed burner should be used in industrial plant with a 30% of hydrogen in volume with no need of hardware modifications. The oxidation investigation on atmospheres deriving from the combustion of 100% of hydrogen, at 1230 °C, showed a moderate scale increase up to 14% for F22V grade and 8% for Inconel[®] 625. This increase of scale growth has not detrimental effect on the scale removability. For the selected reference industrial scenario, the burner was positively tested in industrial furnace with a 30% of hydrogen in volume with no need of hardware modifications. Moderate scale growth was observed, but with no detrimental effect on the scale removability. Moreover, the H₂ addition allows to get CO₂ reductions, without any noticeable drawback on other process parameters or product quality for this industrial scenario.

Keywords: hydrogen / oxidability / descaling susceptibility / decarbonisation / CO₂

1 Introduction

The decarbonization of steel industry requires the adoption of new technologies and the substitution of fossil fuels with alternative energy vector and carbon bearing materials. There is a growing consensus that green hydrogen has a pivotal role to play in achieving deep decarbonisation in an affordable and competitive manner, not least because it offers a way to leverage the significant gas infrastructure asset in Europe (2.2 million kilometers of gas pipelines and 1,200 TWh of underground storage capacity). Enabling this requires the development of a hydrogen-ready value chain – including transport, storage, distribution, and applications for final consumption.

Up today most of the combustion systems used in steel industry for products reheating and treatment are based on natural gas (NG) burners. Alternative fuels, such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), Blast Furnace Gas (BFG), Coke Oven Gas (COG), syngas from biomass and sometime oil are used. The combustion of these fuels has been extensively studied, developed and documented in several European Projects and scientific literature, to improve the energy efficiency and consequently reduce the CO₂, to minimise the Green House Gas (GHG) emission with particular focus on NO_x and at the same time improve the productivity and quality of the product. The most important European Projects in combustion studies are REGTGF [1], NOX-RF [2] and CO2RED [3] and HELNOX-BFG [4]. REGTGGF was focused on innovative burner design, with the aim of reducing energy consumption, CO and NO_x emissions, and improving product quality analysing the impact on scale formation. NOX-RF

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Table 1. Chemical composition of material.

Material	Chemical analysis (%weight)									
	C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cr	Mo	V	Fe	Nb + Ta
A/SA 336 Grade F22V	≤0.15	≤0.60	≤0.007	≤0.004	≤0.10	2.0–2.50	0.9–1.1	0.25–0.35	Balance	
Inconel[®] 625	≤0.1	≤0.5			≤0.5	20–23	8–10		≤5	3.15–4.15

was based on testing and modelling flameless low NO_x burners for both high temperature air combustion and oxy-fuel combustion. CO2RED demonstrated the capability of new combustion technology to allow a step change in environmental impact of reheating furnaces reducing, at the same time, the CO₂ and the NO_x emissions, without impairing steel quality. HELNOX-BFG had, as its objective, the developing of a combustion system for an efficient utilization of blast furnace gas (BFG) in steel reheating furnaces, by fuel preheating (gas-gas heat exchangers or regenerators), to maintain the same production level of a high heating value fuel and reducing natural gas dependence and CO₂ emissions. From a point a view of quality product a very extent of European Projects and literature papers are focused on surface conditioning with reference to scale oxidation and scale removal susceptibility. Among European Project, CONSTOX [5] is dedicated to the effect of atmosphere derived from fuels, such as COG and BFG in comparison to NG, whereas HiPerScale [6] is focused on the scale formation and related impact or steel quality with the aim to individuate new system of protection of surface from the oxidation, as coating, verifying its effect also in descaling susceptibility.

In this frame, SNAM is verifying the opportunity to supply the customers of its network with Natural Gas added with gradually increasing concentrations of hydrogen (H₂). Technical aspects and in general criticalities relevant to the use of mixtures hydrogen-natural gas in industrial processes were investigated with reference to the field of large industrial gas users as Forgiatura A. Vienna (FAV). In particular, main objectives are to evaluate:

- the suitability of existing industrial burners of a reference FAV furnace, not specifically designed for H₂NG blends, to burn gas with increased hydrogen content by experimental campaigns at the CSM-RINA Combustion Studies Experimental Station;
- the effect on oxidability and descaling susceptibility of stocks treated in the furnace for effect of change of flue gas atmosphere due to different of fuel composition. The evaluation is performed by thermal treatment of steel samples in laboratory furnaces, simulating the atmosphere of NG/H₂ blend burners and descaling tests in pilot facility;
- the industrial scaling up on furnace of FAV by the analysis of results performed on the burner and materials tests.

2 Materials and methods

The feasibility study was focused mainly on three aspects:

- feasibility study to use a blend of H₂NG focused on combustion efficiency & emissions and product characteristics;

- experimental tests with various H₂NG blends with the aim to evaluate the effects on combustion & product and the identification of a feasible blending threshold. In particular:

- the evaluation of performance of burner has the aim to select the chemical composition of the H₂NG blend that guarantee the ignition and the stability of burner without heavy hardware modifications,
- the evaluation of the effect on the product has the aim to guarantee that the selected H₂NG blend composition is not detrimental for the quality of final stock;
- industrial tests to validate that the select H₂NG blend should be applicable.

The reference industrial scenario is a FAV treatment furnace for steels & alloys with a capacity 15 t. The furnace employs six high speed burners with diffuser in SIC and feed by cold air.

The products selected for the evaluation of the quality performance are A/SA 336 Grade F22V and Inconel[®] 625 that present different susceptibility to the oxidation. The chemical composition is reported in the Table 1.

In the following sections are reported the description of test rig for the assessment of burner performance and the facilities for the evaluation of oxidability and descaling susceptibility.

2.1 Burner performance and test rig description

To understand if the current combustion system can work with a H₂/NG blend, it is necessary to verify:

- if and in which range of fuel and air flow rate the burner ignites and it is stable;
- the burner behavior at high temperature in terms of emissions, with specific focus on NO_x emissions.

In fact, the higher reactivity of hydrogen respect NG is expected to cause an increase of NO_x formation. In particular, this effect is expected to be larger for an anchored flame burner, as that considered in this study, than for burner that operates in flameless combustion.

The ignition test should be performed on air and in the furnace: in both case the value of the fuel and air flow rate, the fuel and air pressure and the Ionization current are measured during the experimental test. The output the experimentation is the composition blend at which the burner is ignites and is stable without modification of setting burner [7].

The evaluation of the behaviour at high temperature is performed in a furnace adequate to the maximum thermal power (300 kW). The combustion chamber is a section of 1 × 1.5 m and length 4.4 m.

Fig. 1. Layout of system monitoring and test rig.

During the experimental campaign the following measuring systems were available:

- temperature control system composed by different thermocouples that allows mapping the thermal field inside the furnace chamber;
- flow rate control system composed by calibrated orifices and mass meters;
- pressure control system that allows measuring the pressures of all fluids supplied in the furnace and of the furnace chamber;
- monitoring flue gas composition analysis in different points inside the furnace chamber or at the stack. The following emissions could be analyzed:

- Oxygen O_2 [0–21]%,
- Carbon dioxide CO_2 [0–20]%,
- Carbon monoxide CO [0–200] ppm, [0–20]%,
- Nitrogen monoxide NO [0–200] ppm, [0–2000] ppm.

A catalytic converter allows reducing the fraction of NO_2 in flue gas to NO , avoiding the risk of underestimating emissions.

A camera allows monitoring the behaviour of the flame inside the furnace chamber. The installation of devices is customizable, all measured data are collected by a supervisor, that check the burner status and acts to keep safe the plant. Figure 1 shows the layout of system monitoring and test rig.

The outputs are the CO , NO_x emissions at different level of oxygen excess, process temperature and turn down with the selected H_2/NG blend composition (30% and 50% of hydrogen in the NG). The process parameters used for the experimental test are the following:

- rating: 300 kW;
- fuel:
 - NG (for comparison),
 - 30% H_2 –70% NG vol.,
 - 50% H_2 –50% NG vol.,
- air temperature: 25 °C;
- furnace temperature: 950–1100 °C;
- O_2 in flue gas: 1–2–3% dry vol.;
- turn down: 60%, 80%, 100%;
- furnace pressure: 17–20 Pa.

2.4 Oxidability: equipment description

The evaluation of the oxidability [8,9] was performed by the employ of the thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) that, measuring the weight gain, allows to assess the scale growth for a defined process condition (temperature and atmosphere). Main features of the equipment are following reported:

- type of TGA: non-commercial; vertical electrical furnace with dynamic balance, controlled atmosphere;
- specimen size: 50 mm × 50 mm × 5 mm;
- max. weight of specimen for your TGA: 150 g;
- typical temperature profile/heating rate: 2–6 [K/min];
- atmosphere: N_2 , O_2 , CO_2 , H_2O ;
- max. temperature: 1600 °C;
- cooling rate: 2–10 [K/min];
- atmosphere for cooling: inert.

The apparatus has a vertical alumina tube furnace (internal diameter: 50 mm, total length: 790 mm) that can operate at a maximum temperature of 1600 °C. Cooled flanges are located at the top and bottom of the tube and two caps close the furnace preventing air ingress. The upper cooler part of the furnace allows the sample to be maintained under inert atmosphere until the central part has reached the selected temperature. The upper cap has a hole to accommodate the alumina rod from which the specimen is suspended. The lower cap has a hole for a thermocouple the tip of which is located just below the specimen. A hole at one side of the cap provides the inlet of the gas that flows upwards. The furnace atmosphere is prepared by mixed from N_2 , O_2 , CO_2 from bombs, flow rate of each gas being controlled by a flow meter. The reactive gas can be humidified by bubbling through water at a set temperature in order to obtain the target concentration of H_2O . The gas outlet is connected to a probe to monitor the composition of the exit gas using a mass spectrometer.

For each trial a specimen was positioned in the upper part of the furnace, nitrogen was then supplied during the heating stage until the set temperature was reached; the oxidizing atmosphere was then fed to the furnace and the sample was lowered to the hot zone. After oxidation, the sample was cooled in inert atmosphere in the upper part of the furnace. The temperature was monitored and

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the apparatus for thermogravimetric test of steel oxidation.

Table 2. A/SA 336 Grade F22V and Inconel[®] 625 chemical composition.

	C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cr	Mo	V	Fe	Nb+Ta
A/SA 336 Grade F22V	≤0.15	≤0.60	≤0.007	≤0.004	≤0.10	2.0 ÷ 2.50	0.9–1.1	0.25 ÷ 0.35	Bal.	–
Inconel[®] 625	≤0.1	≤0.5	–	–	≤0.5	20 ÷ 23	8–10	–	≤5	3.15 ÷ 4.15

Table 3. TGA tests matrix.

Fuel composition	Flue gas composition, %vol				Temperature 1 Heat treatment 900 °C	Temperature 2 Re-heating 1230 °C	
	O ₂	CO ₂	H ₂ O	N ₂	A/SA 336 Grade F22V	A/SA 336 Grade F22V	Inconel [®] 625
NG	1.8	8.8	17.6	Bal.	X	X	X
50%H₂–50%NG	1.8	6.9	20.7	Bal.	X	X	
H₂	1.6		32.3	Bal.	X	X	X

recorded during the whole trial: heating, soaking and cooling. Figure 2 shows a schematic representation of the apparatus.

The material used for the test were A/SA 336 Grade F22V and Inconel[®] 625 by different oxidation susceptibility. Table 2 shows the typical chemical composition. The reference process conditions were 1230 °C and 900 °C for temperature, simulating a re-heating and a heat treatment, and 3 types of atmospheres corresponding to the flue gas composition of combustion of natural gas, 50% of H₂ in NG and 100% H₂ with air considering of oxygen excess of 1%. Table 3 reports the tests matrix.

2.5 Descaling susceptibility: pilot plant description

The descaling susceptibility of steel surface, under same scale morphology, is intrinsically linked to thermal effect

prior/during and after descaler due to the water cooling and to mechanical impact (normal/shear) of the water jet in striking the surface [10–13]. In particular, the thermal effect is the result of the temperature gradient between the descaling water and the steel or between the air and the steel when the manufactures (slab, bar etc.) are taken out of the furnace, whereas the mechanical impact is due to the force exerted by the water jets on the surface of the scale (impact pressure) which can produce displacement of the scale if porosity or detachment exist as a result of either scaling conditions or thermal contraction effects.

The thermal effect is “represented” by the and S.W.I. (Specific Water Impingement) [l/m²] expressed as:

$$S.W.I = \frac{Q}{Lv},$$

Fig. 3. Descaling map that define the descaling ability during test.

where Q is the nozzle flow rate in l/s, L is the mark length and v is the pipe speed under the descaler in m/s.

The mechanical pressure effect is represented by the impact pressure expressed as:

$$I.P. = \frac{F}{A} = \frac{K'Q\sqrt{2rP}}{H^2},$$

where Q is the nozzle flow rate in l/s, P is the water pressure in Pa, H is the vertical distance in m, ρ is the water density kg/m^3 and K' is a constant which depends on the spray and the thickness angles.

The S.W.I. and I.P. parameters define the conditions which allow to descale and to identify the domain which the two effects, thermal and the mechanical, becomes successful in the descaling process. Figure 3 shows the combination of impact pressure and Specific Flow Impingement used for the descaling trials. If the scale is completely removed in the descaling area the map of descalability field should be carried out.

The descaling susceptibility was evaluated by descaling tests in a pilot plant (see Fig. 4) having the following features:

- *reheating system*: two furnaces able to operate up to 1300 °C in different atmospheres (170 kw burners for combustion of NG or other alternative mixtures as NGH_2 with O_2 in the range 0.2–4%, air or inert). Gas analysis (CO , CO_2 , O_2);
- *sample handling and transfer system*: automatic arm for introduction and extraction of the specimen in the furnaces and transfer of the specimen under the descaler up to 5 m/s;
- *descaler head with nozzles*: variable type, size and geometry, up to two nozzles in line;
- *hydraulic system*: Hammelman high pressure pump up to 400 bar, 137 L/min;
- *cooling area* with inert gas and deoxidizing powder addition;
- *specimens*: $200 \times 300 \times 10$ (L \times W \times T; mm), up to 20 kg;
- control process system and data recording.

The descaling parameters used for the experimental campaign are in the range 0.3–0.6 MPa of impact pressure and in the range 15–20 L/m^2 of S.W.I at the temperature in furnace of 1230 °C. The descaling trials were performed with 100%vol. NG and 50%vol. H_2 in NG.

The criteria for descaling ability were the visual aspect and the metallographic analysis of the samples after descaling test. An example of the visual aspect results is reported in the Figure 5.

3 Technical feasibility

A preliminary technical feasibility was performed for the use of H_2NG blends to evaluate the differences in terms of efficiency/emissions compared to the use of NG, the effects on the treated product and any critical issues related to the components.

Hydrogen and methane (the largest component of natural gas) as well as having a very different low heating value (LHV: 10800 kJ/Nm^3 of hydrogen vs about LHV: 35,800 kJ/Nm^3 of methane), also have different combustion ratios, or require different oxygen values to complete combustion. In fact, comparing the complete combustion reactions of methane and that of hydrogen we have that: 1 Nm^3 di-methane requires 2 Nm^3 of oxygen and produces 2 Nm^3 of water e 1 Nm^3 di-carbon dioxide. The air required for a complete combustion of methane is 9.52 Nm^3 and the produced flue gas is 10.52 Nm^3 (1.88 Nm^3 of nitrogen):

1 Nm^3 of hydrogen requires 0.5 Nm^3 of oxygen and produces 1 Nm^3 of water. The air required for a complete combustion of methane of hydrogen is è 2.38 Nm^3 and the produced flue gas is 2.88 Nm^3 (1.88 Nm^3 of nitrogen).

Therefore, the addition of hydrogen to natural gas necessarily results in:

- a change in the calorific value of the blend;
- a change in the gas flow rate to maintain the same low heating value;
- a change in the air flow rate required for combustion;
- and consequentially variation of the flue gas flow rate.

To better highlight the above, the effect of the hydrogen content in an H_2NG mixture was evaluated by comparing the variation in the flow rates of combustible gas, air and flue gas at the same thermal power and excess air.

Figure 6 shows the flow rates of fuel blends, combustion air and flue gas produced at the same thermal load (1 MW, excess 1% O_2 vol, dry flue gas): it can be observed that as the hydrogen fraction in the blends increases, the volumetric flow rate of the fuel gas increases more than linearly as a combined effect of the lower LHV (low heating value). On the other hand, regarding the combustion air and the fumes produced, their flow rate decreases with the

Fig. 4. Descaling experimental facility.

Fig. 5. Example of visual aspect and the metallographic analysis after test.

Fig. 6. Air, fuel and flue gas flow rate evolution vs H₂ increase in NG.

Fig. 7. Flue gas composition evolution vs. H₂ increase in NG.

increase of the hydrogen fraction, due to the different intake of air necessary to complete the combustion and the decrease of the flue gas that develops (see Eqs. (1) and (2)).

Figure 7 shows the CO₂ and H₂O content in the combustion flue gas with the same reference conditions (1 MW, O₂ excess 1%, DFG). H₂O increases from a content of 18% in the case of natural gas only to 33% in the case of

hydrogen only. The CO₂ content instead decreases from the value of about 9% for the NG combustion to 0% for 100%vol H₂.

The percentage reduction of CO₂ is shown in Figure 8, both as a function of the hydrogen content in the gas mixture (red curve) and as a function of the thermal load supplied with hydrogen. The same data are given for clarity

H2 vol.% in H2NG	H2%rate*	CO2 red., %
0%	0%	0%
10%	3%	3%
20%	7%	7%
30%	11%	11%
40%	17%	17%
50%	23%	23%
60%	31%	31%
70%	41%	41%
80%	55%	55%
90%	73%	73%
100%	100%	100%

Reference: Thermal load 1 MW, 1%O₂ in the furnace

*Percentage of thermal load to the H₂

Fig. 8. Evolution of the reduction of the CO₂ vs. increase of H₂ in the H₂NG blend.

H2%rate (thermal load due to H2 in the H2/NG)	0%	3%	7%	11%	17%	23%	31%	41%	55%	73%	100%
H2 vol.% in H2 NG	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	100%
Specific cons, Nm³/ton	50	54	58	64	70	77	86	98	114	135	167

Fig. 9. Reduction of CO₂ production for several specific consumption.

also in the table: with 10%vol of hydrogen in mixture it is possible to have a reduction of CO₂ of 3%, that increases to 11% for a 30%vol. of H₂, and then to 23% for a blend 50% H₂-50%NG.

Based on the specific consumption of the furnace and the hourly productivity, it is possible to estimate the reduction of the specific quantity of CO₂ per unit of product: for productions up to 200 t/h of steel it is possible to have a reduction of 4 to 6 t/h of CO₂ (see Fig. 9). The first graph (CO₂ reduction vs thermal load due to H₂ in the H₂NG blend) reports the CO₂ saving when a certain percentage of the thermal load is supplied by hydrogen. The second graph (CO₂ reduction vs. H₂ in the H₂NG blend) reports the CO₂ saving when a certain percentage of hydrogen is used in the mix with natural gas. In the table the corresponding numerical values and the fuel flow rate normalized per ton of produced steel (specific

consumption) are reported. As the percentage of H₂ in the blend increases, the fuel flow rate increases due to the lower heating value of hydrogen per unit of volume.

In terms of NO_x emissions, the main difference between hydrogen and methane from the point of view of combustion mechanisms is the different reactivity of the two substances. In particular, while methane is the least reactive alkane of its entire series, hydrogen has a very high reactivity and superior to that of all others. The adiabatic temperature of combustion calculated at constant pressure is higher for hydrogen (2045 °C) than methane (1875 °C). However, since the combustion of hydrogen produces a volume of flue gas much lower than that of methane and the amount of energy emitted by the combustion of hydrogen is less than 1/3 of that delivered by methane, at the rise in flame temperature is extremely limited. Due to the high reactivity, it is expected that the

Table 4. Main combustion features for the selected H₂NG blend.

Fuel composition (%vol)	100%CH ₄	30%H ₂ -70%CH ₄	50%H ₂ -50%NG
Density [kg/Nm ³]	0.70	0.52	0.40
O ₂ stech [Nm ³ /Nm ³ fuel]	2	1.55	1.25
AIR stech [Nm ³ /Nm ³ fuel]	9.52	7.38	5.95
CO ₂ [Nm ³ /Nm ³ fuel]	1	0.7	0.5
H ₂ O [Nm ³ /Nm ³ fuel]	2	1.7	1.5
LHV [kJ/Nm ³]	35835	28325	23318
Fuel flow rate [Nm³/h] at 300 kW	30	39	47

Table 5. Test matrix.

Fuel compositions (%vol)	Fuel flow rate at 100% rate	Fuel flow rate at 80% rate	Fuel flow rate at 60% rate	Temperature furnace [°C]	O ₂ in flue gas (dry vol)
100NG	30	24	18		
30H ₂ -70NG	38	31	23	950-1000-1100	1-2-3
50H ₂ -50NG	47	37	28		

production of nitrogen oxides in a stable hydrogen flame tends to be higher than the combustion of natural gas [7].

Summarizing, the 30% and the 50%vol. of H₂ in the blend are considered interesting for the experimental campaign, because allow to reduce up to 23% of CO₂ and the increase of NO_x should be not too much heavy. [Table 4](#) reports main combustion features (gas density, combustion air, calculated impact on CO₂ and H₂O in the combustion atmosphere, considering the ref. value of 1 for 100% methane [CH₄] combustion, and the heating value) of the selected H₂NG blends and the fuel flow rate reference used in the experimental trials taking into considerations that the burner has a maximum thermal load of 300 kW.

4 Experimental tests

4.1 Burner performance

The industrial burner installed on FAV reference furnace was tested at the CSM-RINA Combustion Studies Experimental Station with two different level of hydrogen in the NG: at 30% and 50%vol. The burner is a 300 kW high speed burner that work in flame mode with cold air. It is important to point out that the selected combustion system is designed to work with natural gas and the scope of the activity is to study the limit of current system working in blends H₂NG.

The experimental campaign was focused on the evaluation of ignition and stability field and on evaluation of the emissions (NO_x) at high temperature with both blends. The description of test rig is reported in the section Burner Performance and Test Rig description, whereas [Table 5](#) reports the test matrix that summarizes process conditions used for the tests including the fuel flow rate reference for the selected blends.

The experimental trials on air and in the furnace showed that the burner ignites with both mixtures, 30 and 50%vol. of H₂ in NG: with 30%vol. of H₂ the burner is stable, whereas with the 50%vol. of H₂ the burner is unstable as the ignition conditions are not repeatable. Nevertheless, for both blends it is possible to keep the same adjustment of the burner set. In addition, the test has allowed to identify the correct working conditions with heat output comparable to use with 100% NG (300 kW). However, the use of the burner with the H₂NG blends requires a modification of the operating settings due to the different combustion ratio: in particular, as reported in [Table 4](#), it is necessary modify the fuel flow gas to maintain same thermal load and then adequate the air flow rate, in relation to different stoichiometric air necessary to maintain same excess oxygen in flue gas.

For the blend with the 30%vol. of hydrogen the burner ignites and is stable from 40% to 100% of nominal thermal load (300 kW) and for an excess of air up to twice the stoichiometric comburent air. [Figure 10](#) reports the flame burner during the ignition test in the furnace.

[Figure 11](#) shows the burning working at the temperature in the furnace of 950 °C for both blends in comparison to the natural gas.

[Figure 12](#) report NO_x emissions at 950 and 1000 °C furnace temperature at full rate: it is possible to observe that for both mixtures there is an increase up to 10% of emission. At furnace temperature of 950 °C and 1%O₂ excess in flue gas the value increases from 131 to 140 mg/Nm³@3O₂ starting from 100% NG to 50%H₂ in NG.

For lower thermal load, at 80% and 60%, the NO_x emissions increase up to 15%: the value increases from 140 to 170 mg/Nm³@3O₂ starting from 100%vol NG to 50%vol H₂ in NG at furnace temperature of 950 °C and 1%O₂ excess in flue gas ([Fig. 13](#)).

Fig. 10. Ignition test in the furnace.

T:950 °C- NG fuel

T:950 °C- 30%H₂-70%NG fuel

T:950 °C- 50%H₂-50%NG fuel

Fig. 11. Burner hot working (950 °C).

Fig. 12. NO_x emission, 100% Rate, furnace temperature 950 °C.

Fig. 13. NO_x emission, 80 and 60% Rate, furnace temperature 950 & 1000 °C.

Material: A/SA 336 Grade F22V

Temperature 1230°C - Weight gain range: 0-0.35 mg/cm²

Material: Inconel® 625

Temperature 1230°C - Weight gain range: 0-0.35 mg/cm²

Fig. 14. TGA result: heating 1230°C–330 min.

Fig. 15. TGA result: heating 900°C–330 min.

Summarizing, for both blends the burner ignites but with the blend 30%H₂70%NG was more stable. In terms of NO_x emissions increase up to 15%. No soot and CO emissions were detected during the experimental campaign.

The experimental campaign has allowed to identify the correct working conditions with heat output comparable to use with 100% NG (300 kW). However, the use of the burner with the mixture requires a modification of the operating settings due to the different combustion ratio in order to maintain same thermal load and same oxygen excess in the flue gas. For these reasons, the blend 30%H₂–70%NG vol. should be applicable on the industrial furnace

4.2 Effect on quality product: oxidability and scale removal susceptibility

The results of thermogravimetric analysis test performed at 1230 °C for 330 min on F22V and Inconel® 625 are reported in the Figure 14.

In case of steel, A/SA 336 Grade F22V, the increase in scale grown was up to 6% (weight) with atmosphere form combustion of 50%H₂ in NG (vol.) and up to 14% (weight) with atmosphere form combustion of H₂100%vol. respect atmosphere form combustion of only NG.

In case of Inconel® 625 the increase was up to 8% with atmosphere form combustion of H₂ 100%vol. respect atmosphere form combustion of only NG. It's important to remark that between steel and superalloy there are, as expected, three orders of magnitude of weight gain.

Figure 15 shows the result of the TGA test at 900 °C for 330 min for steel A/SA 336 Grade F22V, the increase in scale grown was less remarkable with atmosphere form combustion of 50%vol H₂ in NG because the differences were within the experimental error. With atmosphere form combustion of H₂ 100% there was the increase rise up to 7% (weight) respect atmosphere form combustion of only NG.

Figure 16 shows the metallographic investigations A/SA 336 Grade F22V, performed on samples after TGA, by optical microscope and/or SEM analysis in order to evaluate the scale morphology and thickness.

The scale growth was up to 44% in thickness in case of re-heating at 1230 °C with combustion of 100H₂ (3260 vs. 4700 μm), the scale seams was more porose but with similar interface to the one obtained by the combustion of only NG.

The technological tests of oxide removability were performed as illustrated in the section Descaling susceptibility: pilot plant description. on F22V material. The Figure 17 shows the visual aspect of samples after descaling test in atmosphere with natural gas and for comparison 50%H₂–50%NG vol.

The results showed that the material had the same descaling susceptibility using an atmosphere deriving form 50%H₂–50%NG in comparison to NG.

5 Industrial trial

In relation to the results achieved on the burner performance and material quality the mixture of 30%H₂

Fig. 16. Metallographic investigation on A/SA 336 Grade F22V.

Fig. 17. Visual aspect of sample after descaling test (A/SA 336 Grade F22V).

in NG were identified as potentially applicable in the plant for the furnace selected as industrial scenario. This furnace is a chamber used for heat treatments of steels & alloys and has a maximum capacity of 15t and the burners work in ON/OFF conditions at the maximum thermal load (300 kW).

Before industrial testing, an activity to design and implement the system for the abduction of the selected H₂/NG blend to the furnace and verify the compliance to ATEX Directives [14,15] were carried out. A specific thermal treatment of the material was individuated (among the current furnaces industrial operating practices)

Fig. 18. Temperature Profile used for the industrial test.

to evaluate the furnace performance with the selected blend in comparison to 100%vol of natural gas; the temperature references for selected heat treatment are 600 °C and 800 °C (Fig. 18). During the heat treatment the concentrations of emissions at the stack (O_2 , NO_x , CO and CO_2) were monitored.

During the campaign with the H_2/NG blends the furnace worked regularly and the burner operated as required giving at the flame stable for the whole test duration. The NO_x measurements showed an increase with the H_2/NG blend from 5% up to 40% in relation to the furnace temperature and to operating conditions modality of the furnace: in particular, at lower temperature of treatment (600 °C) the NO_x emissions increase less than 10% (95 vs. 100 $mg/Nm^3@3\%O_2$), whereas at higher temperature (800 °C) the NO_x about 40% (104 vs. 145 $mg/Nm^3@3\%O_2$). The increase detected at 800 °C measured in industrial furnace resulted higher than one observed on tests carried at RINA combustion station mainly because the burner works ON/OFF modality and ignites for a very short time determining a subsequent turbulence, air mixing and subsequent NO_x formation increase. An optimization in the operating set of ON/OFF modality should be reduce the increase of NO_x at highest temperature.

6 Discussion of results

The feasibility study remarks that the modification of the H_2 amount in the blend determines a significant modification of flow rate of all fluids (fuel, air and flue gas) and this requires an assessment of these effect not only on the burner, but also on the operating setting of furnace (e.g setting of different air/fuel ratio and air, flow rate reference pressure values).

The experimental campaign on burner using the selected H_2NG blends has highlighted that it is possible to ignite the burner for both mixtures, but that the burner was more stable with the 30% H_2 in NG. When the burner was used with continuous working the increase of NO_x emissions was at maximum the 15% of the value of Natural gas, because the burner was equipped with a quarl that minimizes the effect of the furnace temperature. In the case of working on ON/Off modality, operating conditions on

industrial furnace, the increase of the NO_x emissions may be higher as observed during the industrial campaign. The different final behaviour confirms that the analysis of operating conditions of the furnace is fundamental to correctly evaluate the industrial application of any blends.

On the other hand, considering the aspects relating to product quality, the TGA analysis has highlighted that:

- for heating at high temperature, as 1230 °C, as in a reheating furnace, with flue gas deriving from 100% H_2 , the gain weight is moderate for F22V that rises up 14% and is less significant for the Inconel® 625 (gain weight up to 7%);
- for heating at 900 °C, as in heat treatment, with an atmosphere deriving from the combustion of a blend 50% H_2 -50%NG vol the differences are negligible (for the material more susceptible to the oxidation F22V).

The application of the blend with the 30% of H_2 in NG should be considered conservative to maintain same quality on the product.

The industrial trial highlight that the blend with 30% vol of H_2 in NG can be used in the existing furnace, with quite stable flame condition, although minor furnace adaptation on operating setting should contribute to reduce the increase of NO_x emissions (a modification of operating furnace set may reduce the NO_x increase from 40% to 15% as showed in the pilot plant campaign).

On the base of these evidence, it is possible to concludes that, for this reference industrial scenario, the burner was positively tested with a 30% H_2 in volume with no need of hardware modifications. Moderate scale growth was observed, but with no detrimental effect on the scale removability. Moreover, the H_2 addition allows to get CO_2 reductions, without any noticeable drawback on other process parameters or product quality for this industrial scenario.

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